

Extraction chromatographic studies of copper(II) and bismuth(III) with Aliquat-336

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Abstract : A selective method has been developed for extraction chromatographic studies of Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} with Aliquat-336 (liquid anion exchanger) coated on silica gel as a stationary phase. Quantitative extraction of Cu^{II} has been achieved at 4.0–6.0 M HCl and quantitative extraction of Bi^{III} has been achieved at 0.1–4.0 M HCl, 0.1–6.0 M HNO_3 and 1.0–3.0 M H_2SO_4 . The effects of different acids, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution have been investigated. Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} have been separated from several metal ions. In order to assess the possible analytical application, both the metal ions have been separated from several multicomponent mixtures containing metal ions commonly associated with it. Attempts have been made to extract Cu^{II} from standard alloy and ore samples. The proposed method is simple, rapid and selective.

Keywords : Extraction chromatography, Aliquat-336, multicomponent separation, exchange capacity.

Introduction

Copper is an important transition element for industry. It forms alloys with several metals and is also used in electrical and insecticide industries. On the other hand, bismuth is an important non-transition element commonly associated with elements like Pb, Cu and Zn. It is used in the manufacture of low melting alloys and its salts are also used in pharmaceutical preparations. So industrial effluents contain commonly associated elements along with copper and bismuth. Therefore, it was considered worthwhile to explore an exchange chromatographic method for the separation of both the metal ions from their associated contaminants. Extraction chromatographic studies of Cu^{II} on a silica gel column coated with high molecular weight carboxylic acid like Versatic 10 (C_{10} monocarboxylic acid) has been reported¹. The equilibrium and kinetics of solvent extraction of Cu^{II} from aqueous solutions containing equimolar EDTA with Aliquat-336 in *n*-decanol and kerosene at 298 K were investigated². The extraction behaviour of Cu^{II} has also been studied with Aliquat-336/PVC based polymer liquid membrane³. Bismuth was separated from various metal ions by means of cellulose ion exchanger Cellex P containing phosphonic groups using tetrene as complexing agent⁴. Separation of Bi^{III} from other metal ions by solvent extraction with high molecular weight amines from sodium succinate solution adjusted to suitable pH has been reported⁵. Cyanex-

925 in xylene was used for extraction and separation of Bi^{III} from aqueous solution⁶. The extraction chromatographic method is useful for separation and preconcentration of metal ions. In continuation to the earlier studies⁷, the results of extraction chromatographic behaviour of Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} on silica gel column impregnated with high molecular weight amine, Aliquat-336 from chloride medium are presented in the present investigation. The extracted species in hydrochloric acid medium of Cu^{II} will be⁸ $[\text{CuCl}_4]^{2-}$. The hydrogen bonding of the Aliquat-336 cations $[(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17})_3(\text{CH}_3)\text{N}]^+$ to the chlorides of the $[\text{CuCl}_4]^{2-}$ anion stabilises the square planar geometry⁹.

Results and discussion

The systematic studies on extraction chromatographic behaviour of Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} with Aliquat-336, coated on silica gel in different acids at different concentrations showed that Cu^{II} is quantitatively extracted in HCl medium in the concentration range 4.0–6.0 M, whereas Bi^{III} is quantitatively extracted in 0.1–4.0 M HCl, 0.1–6.0 M HNO_3 and 1.0–3.0 M H_2SO_4 medium. Incomplete extraction of Cu^{II} has been observed in HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 media. 5.0 M HCl gave best extraction result for Cu^{II} .

Stripping agents : After extraction, in order to select specific stripping agent for quantitative elution of Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} from the column, different concentration of acids such as HNO_3 , H_2SO_4 , HCl, CH_3COOH , salt solu-

tion of NaNO₃ and deionised water were tested. It was observed that quantitative recovery of Cu^{II} is possible with 0.05–0.5 M NaNO₃, 0.01–6.0 M HNO₃, 0.01–1.5 M HCl, 0.01–1 M CH₃COOH and also with deionised water. Of these eluents, deionised water and 0.1 M NaNO₃ were found to be most suitable eluent for elution of Cu^{II} and 1.5–2.5 M CH₃COOH for elution of Bi^{III}.

Separation of Cu^{II} from binary mixture : It was possible to separate Cu^{II} from several metal ions in binary mixtures by exploiting the differences in acid concentration for extraction and by using selective eluting agents. Binary mixtures with Cu^{II} in 1.5 M HCl, Hg^{II}, Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ga^{III} and U^{VI} were extracted into the column but Cu^{II} passed through the column. After extraction Fe^{III} was eluted with 0.1 M NaNO₃, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ga^{III} and U^{VI} were eluted with deionised water and Pd^{II} and Cr^{III} was eluted with 6.5 M HNO₃. Binary mixtures containing Cu^{II} with Zn^{II} and Ce^{IV} were passed separately through the column at 0.05 M HCl where Zn^{II} and Ce^{IV} were extracted whereas Cu^{II} was passed through the column with the mobile phase. Zn^{II} was eluted with deionised water and Ce^{IV} was eluted with 6.5 M HNO₃. Binary separation of Cu^{II} and Th^{IV} was achieved by passing the mixture at 5.0 M HCl, Th^{IV} passed through the column with the mobile phase. Cu^{II} was extracted and eluted with deionised water. Binary separation of Cu^{II} and In^{III} was achieved by passing the mixture at 5 M HCl into the column, where both the metal ions were extracted. Cu^{II} was eluted first with deionised water followed by In^{III} with 0.1 M NaNO₃. After separation, all the metal ions were estimated complexometrically with EDTA using xylenol orange indicator¹⁰. The results of binary separations of Cu^{II} with other metal ions are given in Table 1.

Separation of Bi^{III} from binary mixture : It was possible to separate Bi^{III} from several metal ions in binary mixtures by exploiting the differences in acid concentration for extraction and by using selective eluting agents. Binary mixtures containing Bi^{III} and Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pd^{II}, Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, Ga^{III} and U^{VI} were passed separately through the column at 1.5 M HCl where all the diverse ions were co-extracted along with Bi^{III}. After extraction Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ga^{III} and U^{VI} were eluted with deionised water, Pd^{II} and Cr^{III} were eluted with 6.5 M HNO₃ and Fe^{III} was eluted with 0.1 M NaNO₃ followed by Bi^{III} with 2.0 M CH₃COOH. At 1.25 M HCl, binary mixture containing Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, La^{III}, Al^{III} and Co^{II} with Bi^{III} were passed

Table 1. Separation of Cu^{II} from binary mixtures

Cu^{II} taken = 1.84 mg, column : 0.8 × 6.5 cm,
Flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹

Metal ion	W _{metal} (mg)		Recovery of Cu ^{II} (%)	Eluent used
	Added	Recovered		
Hg ^{II}	2.85	2.87	100.7	H ₂ O
Fe ^{III}	1.94	1.92	98.9	0.1 M NaNO ₃
Cr ^{III}	1.14	1.15	100.9	6.5 M HNO ₃
Pb ^{II}	2.36	2.34	99.1	H ₂ O
Cd ^{II}	4.04	4.06	100.5	H ₂ O
Pd ^{II}	2.66	2.64	99.2	6.5 M HNO ₃
Ga ^{III}	1.44	1.43	99.3	H ₂ O
U ^{VI}	2.57	2.55	99.2	H ₂ O
Zn ^{II}	2.09	2.11	100.9	H ₂ O
Ce ^{IV}	3.81	3.78	99.2	6.5 M HNO ₃
Th ^{IV}	2.18	2.18	100	–
In ^{III}	2.74	2.76	100.7	0.1 M NaNO ₃

through the column with the mobile phase and only Bi^{III} was extracted which was eluted with 2.0 M CH₃COOH. Binary separation of Bi^{III} and Zn^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture at 1.25 M HCl where both the metal ions were extracted. Bi^{III} was eluted with 2.0 M CH₃COOH followed by Zn^{II} with deionised water. Binary mixtures containing Bi^{III} and Cu^{II}, In^{III} were passed separately through the column at 3.5 M HCl where all the diverse ions were co-extracted with Bi^{III}. Cu^{II} and In^{III} were eluted with deionised water and 0.1 M NaNO₃ respectively followed by Bi^{III} with 2.0 M CH₃COOH. Binary separation of Bi^{III} and Ce^{IV} was achieved by passing the mixture at 0.05 M HCl through the column, where both the metal ions were extracted. Bi^{III} was eluted first with 2.0 M CH₃COOH followed by Ce^{IV} with 6.0 M HNO₃. After separation, all the metal ions were estimated complexometrically with EDTA using xylenol orange indicator¹⁰. The results of binary separations of Bi^{III} with other metal ions are given in Table 2.

Separation of Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} from multicomponent mixtures : The proposed method was applied to separate Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} from their ternary and quaternary mixtures and results are presented in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively. In almost all the cases quantitative extraction and separation have been achieved. The elution profile of Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} in multicomponent mixture is given in Figs. 1 and 2.

Separation of Cu^{II} from synthetic mixture containing Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 0.05 M HCl. At this con-

Table 2. Separation of Bi^{III} from binary mixtures

Bi^{III} taken = 2.59 mg, column : 0.8 × 6.5 cm,

Flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹

Metal ion	W _{metal} (mg)		Recovery of Bi ^{III} (%)	Eluent used
	Added	Recovered		
Hg ^{II}	2.85	2.87	100.7	H ₂ O
Pb ^{II}	2.36	2.34	99.2	H ₂ O
Cd ^{II}	4.04	4.06	100.5	H ₂ O
Pd ^{II}	2.66	2.64	99.2	6.5 M HNO ₃
Fe ^{III}	1.94	1.92	98.9	0.1 M NaNO ₃
Cr ^{III}	1.14	1.15	100.9	6.5 M HNO ₃
Ga ^{III}	1.44	1.45	100.7	H ₂ O
U ^{VI}	2.57	2.55	99.2	H ₂ O
Th ^{IV}	2.18	2.18	100	-
Zr ^{IV}	2.55	2.52	98.5	-
La ^{III}	2.06	2.03	98.5	-
Al ^{III}	1.28	1.30	101.5	-
Co ^{II}	1.38	1.39	100.7	-
Zn ^{II}	2.09	2.11	100.9	H ₂ O
Cu ^{II}	1.84	1.82	98.9	H ₂ O
In ^{III}	2.74	2.76	100.7	0.1 M NaNO ₃
Ce ^{IV}	3.81	3.78	99.2	6.0 M HNO ₃

dition Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were extracted whereas Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} were passed through the column. Zn^{II} was eluted with deionised water followed by Cd^{II} with 0.5 M NaNO₃. The mobile phase containing Cu^{II} and Hg^{II} was again passed through the column at 1.0 M HNO₃. Cu^{II} was percolated with the mobile phase whereas Hg^{II} was extracted and it was eluted with 0.05 M Na₂SO₄. Separation of Cu^{II}, Fe^{III}, Cr^{III} and Zn^{II} was achieved by passing mixture through the column at 0.05 M HCl, where only Zn^{II} was extracted and the same was eluted with deionised water. The mobile phase containing Cu^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} was again passed through the column at 1.25 M HCl. Under this condition Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} was extracted and Cu^{II} was percolated with the mobile phase. Fe^{III} was eluted with 0.1 M NaNO₃ followed by Cr^{III} with 6.5 M HNO₃.

Separation of Bi^{III} from synthetic quaternary mixture containing Bi^{III}, Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and In^{III} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 1.0 M HCl. Under this condition Bi^{III} and Ga^{III} were extracted whereas Al^{III} and In^{III} were passed through the column. Bi^{III} was eluted with 2.0 M CH₃COOH followed by Ga^{III} with deionised water. The mobile phase containing Al^{III} and

Table 3. Separation of Cu^{II} from multicomponent synthetic mixtures

Column = 0.8 × 6.5 cm, Flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹

Sl. no.	Metal ions in mixture	W _{Added} (mg)	Recovery (%)	Relative error (%)	Eluent used	V _{Eluent} (ml)
1.	Cu ^{II}	1.84	98.9	-1.08	-	25
	Hg ^{II}	2.85	99.3	-0.70	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
	Zn ^{II}	2.09	100.5	+0.48	H ₂ O	30
2.	Cu ^{II}	1.84	100.1	+1.08	-	20
	Pb ^{II}	2.36	99.1	-0.85	H ₂ O	25
	Cd ^{II}	4.04	100.5	+0.49	0.5 M NaNO ₃	30
3.	Cu ^{II}	1.84	100	0	-	20
	Cd ^{II}	4.04	99.5	-0.49	0.5 M NaNO ₃	30
	Pd ^{II}	2.66	100.7	+0.75	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
4.	Cu ^{II}	1.84	100	0	-	20
	Pb ^{II}	2.36	99.1	-0.85	H ₂ O	30
	Pd ^{II}	2.66	99.2	-0.75	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
5.	Cu ^{II}	1.84	100	0	-	20
	Fe ^{III}	1.94	99.5	-0.51	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
	Cr ^{III}	1.14	100.9	+0.87	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
6.	Cu ^{II}	1.84	100	0	H ₂ O	30
	Ga ^{III}	1.44	98.6	-1.39	-	25
	In ^{III}	2.74	100.7	+0.73	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
7.	Cu ^{II}	1.84	98.9	-1.08	-	25
	Fe ^{III}	1.94	99.6	-0.51	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30

8.	Zn ^{II}	2.09	1.00	0	H ₂ O	25
	Cu ^{II}	1.84	98.9	-1.08	-	25
	Th ^{IV}	2.18	100	0	H ₂ O	30
9.	U ^{VI}	2.57	99.2	-0.78	0.1 M HNO ₃	30
	Cu ^{II}	1.84	101.1	+1.08	-	20
	U ^{VI}	2.57	100	0	H ₂ O	25
10.	Ce ^{IV}	3.81	99.2	-0.78	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
	Cu ^{II}	1.84	98.9	-1.08	-	25
	Zn ^{II}	2.09	98.5	-1.43	H ₂ O	30
11.	Cd ^{II}	4.04	99.5	-0.49	0.5 M NaNO ₃	30
	Hg ^{II}	2.85	100.7	+0.70	0.05 M Na ₂ SO ₄	25
	Cu ^{II}	1.84	98.4	-1.63	-	20
	Fe ^{III}	1.94	99.5	-0.51	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
	Cr ^{III}	1.14	101.7	+1.75	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
	Zn ^{II}	2.09	100	0	H ₂ O	30

Table 4. Separation of Bi^{III} from multicomponent synthetic mixturesColumn = 0.8 × 6.5 cm. Flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹

Sl. no.	Metal ions in mixture	W _{Added} (mg)	Recovery (%)	Relative error (%)	Eluent used	V _{Eluent} (ml)
1.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	98.8	-1.16	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Al ^{III}	1.28	100.8	+0.78	-	30
	Fe ^{III}	1.94	100.5	+0.51	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
2.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	100	0	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Fe ^{III}	1.94	100.5	+0.51	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
	Cr ^{III}	1.14	99.1	-0.87	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
3.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	100.4	+0.39	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Ga ^{III}	1.44	98.6	-1.39	H ₂ O	30
	In ^{III}	2.74	100.7	+0.73	-	25
4.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	100.7	+0.77	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Hg ^{II}	2.85	99.3	-0.70	H ₂ O	30
	Pb ^{II}	2.36	99.1	-0.85	1.0 M HNO ₃	25
5.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	98.8	-1.16	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Hg ^{II}	2.85	100.7	+0.70	H ₂ O	25
	Cu ^{II}	1.84	101.1	+1.08	-	30
6.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	100.7	+0.77	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Cu ^{II}	1.84	98.9	-1.08	-	25
	Cd ^{II}	4.04	99.5	-0.49	0.5 M NaNO ₃	30
7.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	99.2	-0.77	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Pb ^{II}	2.36	99.6	-0.42	H ₂ O	30
	Cd ^{II}	4.04	100.5	+0.49	0.5 M NaNO ₃	25
8.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	100.7	+0.77	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Cu ^{II}	1.84	98.9	-1.08	-	30
	Pb ^{II}	2.36	100.4	+0.42	H ₂ O	30
9.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	100.4	+0.39	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Th ^{IV}	2.18	100.9	+0.92	-	25

Table-4 (contd.)

	U ^{VI}	2.57	99.2	-0.78	H ₂ O	25
10.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	100.7	+0.77	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Al ^{III}	1.28	98.4	-1.56	-	30
	Ga ^{III}	1.44	101.4	+1.38	H ₂ O	25
	In ^{III}	2.74	99.3	-0.73	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
11.	Bi ^{III}	2.59	98.4	-1.54	2.0 M CH ₃ COOH	25
	Cu ^{II}	1.84	101.1	+1.08	-	30
	Pb ^{II}	2.36	99.1	-0.85	H ₂ O	30
	Zn ^{II}	2.09	100.5	+0.48	H ₂ O	25

Fig. 1. Separation of Cu^{II} from synthetic multicomponent mixture.

Fig. 2. Separation of Bi^{III} from synthetic multicomponent mixture.

In^{III} was again passed through the column at 3.0 M HCl. Al^{III} was percolated with the mobile phase whereas In^{III} was extracted and it was eluted with 0.1 M NaNO₃. Separation of Bi^{III}, Cu^{II}, Pb^{II} and Zn^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 0.05 M HCl first, where only Zn^{II} was extracted and eluted with deionised water. Mobile phase containing Bi^{III}, Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} was again passed through the column at 0.5 M HCl. Under this condition Bi^{III} and Pb^{II} was extracted and Cu^{II} was percolated with the mobile phase. Bi^{III} was eluted with 2.0 M CH₃COOH followed by Pb^{II} with deionised water.

Extraction of Cu^{II} from standard ore and alloy samples :
To assess the possible analytical applications of the proposed method, the recommended procedure was applied

for the separation of copper from some of the standard ore (copper concentrate) and alloy samples (brass-5 g and H.T. brass-10 g). The solution of the ore and alloy samples were prepared by treating with concentrated HNO₃ (10 ml) and water (5 ml) and digested on a water bath for one hour. The solution was cooled, filtered and diluted with water to a volume of 100 ml and the extraction carried out at 1.0 M HCl medium. Under this condition Cu^{II} was passed through the column with the mobile phase and the other metal ions were extracted. In most of the cases, quantitative separations were achieved (copper concentrate : certified value 23.6%, recovered 22.4%; brass-5 g : certified value 67.4%, recovered 66.8%; H.T. brass-10 g : certified value 60.8%, recovered 60.2%). The obtained

results achieved agree fairly well with the certified values.

Experimental

An Elico LI-120 pH meter with a combined glass electrode and a chromatographic column (Borosil) were used.

The liquid anion exchanger, Aliquat-336 (Fluka, AG), a high molecular mass synthetic quaternary ammonium compound (tricaprylmethylammonium chloride) was used as such. The stock solution of Cu^{II} (1.84 mg ml⁻¹) and Bi^{III} (2.59 mg ml⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving copper(II) sulphate (CuSO₄·5H₂O) and bismuth(III) nitrate [Bi(NO₃)₃·5H₂O] in distilled water respectively, and standardised complexometrically using xylenol orange indicator¹⁰. The ion exchange material was prepared following literature method¹¹.

Extraction procedure : For the extraction of Cu^{II}, 5.0 M HCl (20 ml) was passed through the column (0.8 × 6.5 cm) first, then an aliquot containing 1.84 mg of Cu^{II} in 5.0 M HCl was passed through the column at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. In case of Bi^{III}, 1.5 M HCl (20 ml) was passed through the column (0.8 × 6.5 cm) followed by the aliquot containing 2.59 mg of Bi^{III} in 1.5 M HCl at a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. After extraction, both the metal ions were stripped with different acids, bases and salts of various concentrations and deionised water. Deionised water and 0.1 M NaNO₃ solutions were found to be the best stripping agent for Cu^{II} and 1.5–2.5 M CH₃COOH for Bi^{III}. The amount of Cu^{II} and Bi^{III} were determined complexometrically.

Exchange capacity : The exchange capacity of the exchanger was determined at different temperatures (20–40 °C) measuring milligram equivalents of OH⁻ absorbed by 1 g of dry exchanger in the chloride form¹². The liberated chloride was titrated against standard AgNO₃

solution using potassium chromate indicator¹³. The exchange capacity of the dry exchanger was found to be 0.57 meq g⁻¹.

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